

Impact Factor: 5.479

ISSN 2181-9505

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-9505

Philosophy and Life

FALSAFA VA HAYOT • ФИЛОСОФИЯ И ЖИЗНЬ

Special
Issue 1

2024

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI VAZIRLAR MAHKAMASI
HUZURIDAGI IMOM BUXORIY XALQARO
ILMIY-TADQIQOT MARKAZI
O'ZBEKISTON FALSAFA JAMIYATI

Международный научно-
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Имам Бухари при Кабинете
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FALSAFA VA HAYOT XALQARO JURNAL

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СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫЙ НОМЕР 1

PHILOSOPHY AND LIFE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL
SPECIAL ISSUE 1

Jurnal bir yilda 4
marta nashr qilinadi.

Журнал выходит
4 раза в год.

The journal is published
4 times in a year.

ISSN: 2181-9505
DOI: 10.26739/2181-9505

2024

FALSAFA VA HAYOT XALQARO JURNAL

№SI-1 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9505-2024-SI-1>

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Решением Высшей аттестационной комиссии при Кабинете Министров Республики Узбекистан введен в список специальных журналов. 2018 год 29 декабря протокол №260/7

Регистрационное свидетельство №1175 выдано 27.02.2018 агенством по печати и информации Узбекистана

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№SI-1 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9505-2024-SI-1>

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The registration certificate № 1175 was issued on February 27, 2018 by the Uzbek Agency for Press and Information

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ENGAGEMENT OF MEDICAL STUDENTS IN PROFESSIONAL ETHICAL- DEONTOLOGICAL CULTURE

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11397496>

ABSTRACT

This article explores the concept of deontology and its significance for medical students in higher medical education. It is worth noting that the professional activities of medical professionals inevitably involve a deontological dimension, manifested in a deep understanding by the healthcare worker of their professional and human duty, in high professional and moral-ethical responsibility for the quality of the process and outcome of their professional activities. Deontological norms are the main regulator of the activities of medical professionals, ensuring the functioning of medicine as a socio-professional and moral-ethical system and the sphere of application of the personal qualities of specialists in the medical field as its subjects. In this regard, addressing the issue of shaping the deontological competence of future medical professionals is, in our opinion, one of the most important strategies for the development of pedagogical science.

Keywords: deontology, bioethics, medical student, higher medical school.

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TIBBIYOT TALABALARINI KASBIY AXLOQIY-DEONTOLOGIK MADANIYATGA JALB QILISH

ANNOTATSIYA

ushbu maqolada deontologiya tushunchasi va uning oliy tibbiy ta'limdagi tibbiyot talabalari uchun ahamiyati o'rganiladi. Ta'kidlash joizki, tibbiyot mutaxassislarining kasbiy faoliyati muqarrar ravishda tibbiyot xodimi tomonidan ularning kasbiy va insoniy burchini chuqur anglashda, ularning kasbiy faoliyati jarayoni va natijalari uchun yuqori kasbiy va ma'naviy-axloqiy javobgarlikda namoyon bo'ladigan deontologik o'lchovni o'z ichiga oladi. Deontologik me'yorlar tibbiyot mutaxassislari faoliyatining asosiy regulyatori bo'lib, tibbiyotning ijtimoiy-kasbiy va axloqiy-axloqiy

tizim sifatida ishlashini va tibbiyot sohasidagi mutaxassislarining shaxsiy fazilatlarini uning sub'ekti sifatida qo'llash sohasini ta'minlaydi. Shu munosabat bilan bo'lajak tibbiyot mutaxassislarining deontologik kompetentsiyasini shakllantirish masalasini hal qilish, bizning fikrimizcha, pedagogika fanini rivojlantirishning eng muhim strategiyalaridan biridir.

Kalit so'zlar: deontologiya, bioetika, tibbiyot talabasi, oliy tibbiyot maktabi.

Introduction: The deontological competence of a medical professional represents a characteristic of the individual specialist, enabling them to interact productively with both the internal (professional) and external (social) environments by possessing deontological knowledge, skills, and abilities. This competence is aimed at successful personal-professional interaction with patients and ensuring effective organization of therapeutic and preventive processes, as well as solving professional tasks. It is characterized by the presence of a system of knowledge reflecting the substantive essence of intellectual, worldview, and moral values; the ability to predict and construct the process of professional activity considering its specificity and in the field of interaction with colleagues and patients. This is predetermined by the content of norms of professional medical ethics, moral imperatives, and professional-moral ideals and values of medical activity. The structure of deontological competence is based on moral-ethical attitudes, benchmarks of the socio-professional environment of medical activity, and includes motivational-personal, creative-meaningful, cognitive-deontological, and reflexive components.

The conceptual basis of the problem of forming the deontological competence of future specialists lies in the research fields of pedagogy, psychology, philosophy, sociology, and medicine. In this regard, the works of Z.M. Mukhamedov, Zh.A. Rizaev, A.N. Makhmudova (2021-2024), M.S. Abdullokhodzhaeva, N.E. Gafurova (2017), N.A. Umirzakova (2021) hold determining significance in terms of the researched problem.

The theoretical model of forming the deontological competence of future medical workers, constructed with consideration of the requirements imposed on the professional functionality and quality of deontological training of medical workers (humanism, professionalism, scientific validity, self-criticism, respect for the rights, freedoms, and dignity of patients, relatives of patients, and other persons who may suffer psychological trauma or harm to their physical and mental health), includes functional-target, substantive-activity, managerial-technological, and evaluative-resultant components. The model serves as a theoretical and morally practical guideline for organizing the deontological training of future specialists in medical education and is aimed at the subject-deontological development of the personality of the future medical worker.

The complex of psycho-pedagogical conditions (including the presence of a balanced educational system in the medical college; orientation of the educational process in the medical college towards the subjectivity of the student, capable of self-actualization; utilization of various techniques of deontological training for students, forming a system of knowledge about deontology, professional-communicative culture, mastery of ethical-deontological techniques) ensures the implementation of the model for the formation of deontological competence in the educational-professional space of a medical university.

The mechanism for implementing the model for the formation of deontological competence functions through the sequential stages (analytical-diagnostic, organizational-motivational, functional-implementing, resultative-corrective), covering the researched process from goal setting to analysis of its results, and providing balanced and scientifically grounded management of the formation of deontological competence for medical university students.

The methodology of the research was determined by a number of initial positions, including the focus on forming the deontological competence of future mid-level medical specialists with an orientation towards the requirements for their level of professional training; the formation of the personality of the future medical worker taking into account the prospects of their professional growth and life goals; socially-personal and professionally oriented direction of the conducted activities.

To test the hypothesis and solve the set tasks, a set of research methods was used: theoretical analysis of scientific, philosophical, psycho-pedagogical, and specialized literature on the research

problem; analysis of the professional activities of medical workers, the results of the activities of higher professional education institutions - on the organization of professional training for future specialists; study and generalization of mass innovative pedagogical experience; analysis of the content of specialist training programs; expert assessment and self-assessment; generalization of independent characteristics; pedagogical experiment, during which the following monitoring methods were used: observation, explication as the unfolding of the content of training for future high-level medical specialists; survey methods (interviews, questionnaires, interviews); statistical methods for processing empirical data.

The Degree of Problem Exploration: The issue of responsibility is inherently linked to the evolution of crisis situations (in all their variety), which as a philosophical problem has been addressed in the works of renowned Western philosophers, cultural theorists, sociologists, and psychologists of the past century. The moral-philosophical aspects of responsible worldview are represented in the works of Immanuel Kant, Max Weber, Erich Fromm, and Viktor Frankl. With the emergence and subsequent escalation of ecological problems in the early 20th century, humanist thinkers attempted to develop norms.

One contemporary ethical approach is bioethics and deontology, which are naturally linked to the discourse of ecological and applied ethics. Researchers such as V.R. Potter, E. Pellegrino, T. Beauchamp, J. Childress, D. Callahan, A. Hellegers, and J. Fletcher have pointed out the American origin of bioethics and the specific factors associated with Western cultural traditions. Russian researchers of the second half of the 20th century (I.T. Frolov, A.A. Baev, D.K. Belyaev, I.N. Smirnov) largely laid the groundwork for the further development of the bioethical worldview. Scientists in the field of bioethics, such as B.G. Yudin, P.D. Tishchenko, J.B. Konovalova, A.Ya. Ivanyushkin, and I.V. Siluyanov, have made significant contributions to the development of the bioethical tradition.

Works by Western philosophers such as Hans Jonas, Karl-Otto Apel, Jürgen Habermas, and Francis Fukuyama, whose works are associated with a reevaluation of the foundations of traditional approaches to the study of contemporary ethics of responsibility, have contributed to the underdevelopment of certain aspects of bioethical methodology.

In the context of this research, works in the field of professional morality and psychology of professions were of particular importance. The moral-sociological aspect of professional and medical ethics has been studied based on the works of V.I. Bakhtanovsky, Yu.V. Sogomonov, B.V. Petrovsky, A.Ya. Ivanyushkin, as well as on the basis of research conducted by Russian philosophers, sociologists, educators, and psychologists, where the processes of assimilation of ethical norms and mechanisms of moral development were studied (C.J. Rubinstein, A.I. Titarenko, J.M. Mitina, I.B. Nazarova, V.P. Andronov).

In recent years in Uzbekistan, bioethical research has focused on the problems of professional education of the personality of the future specialist in connection with the increased need of society for the formation of an active, independent, responsible personality capable of productive self-realization in the professional space of modern society by bioethicists, doctors, and philosophers such as Z.M. Mukhamedova, M.S. Abdullokhodzhaeva, N.E. Gafurova, N.A. Umirzakova, A.N. Makhmudova, and Zh.A. Rizaev.

Thus, an analysis of the extent of development of the discussed problem reveals the necessity for further research.

The theoretical and practical significance of the article lies in substantiating the need for the formation of deontological competence in future medical workers in accordance with socio-professional priorities and individual needs of future middle-level medical specialists in productive deontological training, its contribution to the further development of conceptual ideas of the theory and methodology of professional education; the development of didactic representations of the essence of the concept of "deontological competence of a medical worker" taking into account the requirements for the professional functionality of medical specialists; consideration of the theoretical foundations, design of the model for the formation of deontological competence of future medical workers, identification of psycho-pedagogical conditions and development of a mechanism for its

implementation aimed at shaping the personality of the future medical specialist in accordance with the moral-ethical priorities of the modern socio-professional environment of medicine.

Materials of the research can serve as a scientific and methodological basis for specialists (medical workers, psychologists) who are involved in the support of future physicians.

Conclusion: Summarizing all the above, it is possible to make the following conclusions. The conducted research addresses an actual scientific task both in theoretical and applied aspects - the formation of deontological competence in future medical professionals of medical universities. The theoretical aspects of the problem of forming deontological competence of future medical workers, based on the analysis of literary sources from various fields of scientific knowledge, the specifics of the professional activities of medical workers, the range of tasks they solve within the framework of professional functionality, and the results of experimental research, have allowed us to draw a number of conclusions regarding the problem of scientific search and to identify the main directions for further work.

The sphere of medical activity is one of the quite complex, multifaceted, and contradictory spheres of socio-cultural relations, focusing on the character of public relations both between individual subjects and between the individual and society as a whole. At the same time, the fundamental space of such relations is the moral-ethical space of medicine, which significantly influences both the personality of the patient and the personality of the medical worker. In this regard, it seems that without proper moral-ethical education, professional deontological training, a medical worker cannot become a full-fledged, qualified specialist.

In our research, an analysis of the content and specifics of the professional activities of medical professionals at Samarkand State Medical University showed that the activities of medical personnel of this professional level belong to the class of professional activities carried out in the "person - person" system, in which the issues of interaction between a medical worker and a patient are of particular importance based on the deontological basis of the professional activities of a medical worker.

In our research, it is noted that the deontological training of medical workers is the main regulator of the quality of their professional activities, the benchmark and limitation of the application of professional knowledge, skills, and abilities in specific professional situations. The conducted research allowed us to identify the main deontological requirements imposed on medical workers: humanism, professionalism, scientific substantiation, self-criticism, respect for the rights, freedoms, and dignity of patients, relatives of patients, and other individuals who may suffer emotional trauma or harm to their physical and mental health.

In our research, it is shown that a special place in the professional functionality of a medical worker is occupied by deontological competence, which is defined as a personal property of a specialist that allows them to interact productively with the internal (professional) and external (social) environment due to the presence of deontological knowledge and skills, professionally important deontological qualities. The conducted research allowed us to determine the structure of the deontological competence of a medical worker and characterize its individual components (motivational-personal, creative-meaningful, cognitive-deontological, and reflexive).

Theoretical analysis and research of the investigation problem enabled the construction of a pedagogical model for the formation of deontological competence among future medical specialists, medical students, within the educational process at the Samarkand State Medical University. This model is presented in the work through functional-target, substantive-activity, managerial-technological, and evaluative-resultant components. Each component, with its own goals, tasks, functions, and substantive content, constitutes a part of the comprehensive process of forming deontological competence in future medical workers.

The conducted research with the Department of Social and Humanitarian Sciences revealed that for the implementation of the designed model and the conditions ensuring its productivity, an adequate mechanism is necessary. This mechanism should organizationally and methodologically facilitate the process of forming deontological competence, which is realized within the educational

process at a medical university and includes a series of stages (organizational-motivational, analytical-diagnostic, substantive-activity, evaluative-resultant).

The analysis of the organization of the educational process at our university conducted in the work allowed us to conclude that insufficient attention is paid to the study of issues of medical deontology theory and the practice of its application in solving professional tasks.

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ISSN 2181-9505

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-9505

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PHILOSOPHY AND LIFE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL
SPECIAL ISSUE 1

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